

A Study on Nomophobia and Internet Addiction among Students of Arts and Science colleges with reference to Puducherry, India

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Abstract

Background: Nowadays, Problematic smart phone use is widespread, and college-age students faces an especially high risk of its associated consequences. While a promising body of research has emerged in recent years in this area, the domination of quantitative inquiries can be fruitfully and conceptually complemented by perspectives informed through qualitative research. Toward that end, this study aimed to interrogate the myriad behavioral, attitudinal, and psychological tendencies as aside effect of college student's engagement with the smart phone in their everyday lived experience and having risk of developing nomophobia through in-depth interviews. **Methods:** Here decided 82 participants from ten Arts and Science college campuses hailing from different geographic regions in Puducherry, and conducted semi-structured in-depth Questionnaire in the period from July to August 2022. Subjective experiences, personal narratives and individual perceptions in the context of routine interaction with the smart phone were thematically analyzed through a reiterative process in an effort to detect prevailing threads and recurring subthemes. **Results:** The results reveal the frequency and percentage of respondents having risk of developing nomophobia. The data presented results shows that, majority 60% of the respondents were have moderate risk of developing nomophobia, 27% of respondents were at verge of having severe risk of nomophobia, and remaining 13% of respondents are at mild risk e of nomophobia. There was increase in the prevalence of smart phone addiction and nomophobia during the study period as compared to the prevalence from studies which were conducted in the study period. **Conclusion:** Appropriate measures should be taken by colleges and authorities to address an issue of smart phone addiction and nomophobia, so that students can concentrate on their studies at home during the study period.

Keywords: Smartphone addiction, Arts and Science College, Smartphone addiction reasons, undergraduates, nomophobia;

1. Introduction

Today, information and communication technologies have become an integral part of people's lives. Many people, particularly teenagers, spend much of their time with technological devices for studying, for searching for information on the Internet, for playing games, and for communicating. Mobile phone use has been gradually increasing, not only for communication, but also to access internet and social networks (Ayar, Gerçeker, Özdemir, & Bektas, 2018).

Subsequently, the overuse of smart-phones leads to many problems, including social media dependency, Nomophobia, and Problematic Internet Use (PIU), which have negative effects on the psychological, social, academic and professional life of an individual. Nomophobia as new phenomena of negative smart-phone misuse is described as the anxiety and distress experienced by individuals who habitually use Internet-based communication devices, especially when the devices are not available. Users fear that they will not be aware of messages, recent events, and various experiences shared on social media (Choi J, Lee, 2015).

Individuals with Nomophobia continuously check for messages or calls experience anxiety and distress when they are out of the coverage area or mobile phone usage is limited. They tend to keep the phone switched on 24 hours a day, take the smart-phone to bed with them. The use of smart-phones, especially for social connections, is very high among teenagers with social media dependence, who use programs such as Facebook to share experiences and build and maintain social relationships (Khumsri et al., 2015).

Discovering the prevalence of Nomophobia among students is very important, as the misuse of Smart phones, it can lead to poorer academic performance during class (Gutiérrez-Puertas et al., 2019).

More specifically, Smartphone have numerous resources, such as high resolution cameras, that allow personnel to take photos, or record videos or audios that can be shared instantly through networks. Therefore, the advanced functions of Smartphone allow personnel to carry out certain practices in the environment that may result in a breach in confidentiality and privacy, provoking a proliferation of data (Aguilera-Manrique et al., 2018).

Why this study?

Nomophobia among college students is very important problem to be explored, as the misuse of Smart phones do have negative consequences on students' every day activities, cognitive functioning in the form of inattentiveness and distractions, threatening their academic achievements in terms of educational development.

This current research should be useful in raising college students' awareness for deeper understanding of the negative impact of the Nomophobia and Problematic Internet Use

(PIU) on their daily life activities, academic achievements. So, the aim of the current study was to explore the Nomophobia levels among college students at the Arts and Science colleges of Puducherry. The list of Arts and Science colleges in Puducherry as follows: (i) Achariya Arts and Science College, (ii) Achariya School of Business and Technology & Cambrian, (iii) Aditya Institute of Management, Science and Research, (iv) Bharathidasan Government College, (v) Idhaya College of Arts and Science for Women, (vi) Indira Gandhi College of Arts and Science, (vii) Kasthurba College For Women, (viii) Pondicherry University Community College, (ix) Pope John Paul II college of Education, (x) Radha Krishan Arya College, (xi) Rajeswari College of Arts & Science For Women, (xii) Saradha Gangadharan College, (xiii) Tagore Government Arts and Science College, (xiv) Venkateswara College of Education, (xv) Kanchi Mamunivar Centre for Post Graduate Studies (Autonomous), (xvi) Perunthalaivar Kamarajar Arts College, (xvii) RAAK Arts and Science College and (xviii) Villianur College for Women.

2. Background

Without social life, it will be very difficult for human beings to survive and remain mentally healthy. Smart phones have played a major role in establishing and maintaining the social connectivity between the humans even from far distance. Smart phones have become one of the most important integral parts of human life including those college students, because of various functions served by them. Research has shown that smart phones have played a role in making the people socially more active, helped them in their profession, helped them in updating their general knowledge, and helped them in establishing their social identity through use of various applications such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Whats App, and Social Media Apps.

Over the years, and in particular during the 21st century, here it is observed a progressive development of new technologies and devices such as computers, tablets and smart phones; these new devices have completely transformed the way people communicate. Along with the progress of technological development, the shapes of the various devices have also changed, becoming smaller and therefore easy to carry. The ICTs (acronym of Information and Communication Technologies, acronym used by researchers, since the 80s have become particularly widespread and used increasingly in modern cultures and developed countries thanks to their “*ever present*” nature and considered an irreplaceable part of a society in constant connection. Thanks to smart phones, people can research, carry out economic and recreational activities, download learning tools, undertake school research, carry out economic and recreational activities, have easier and faster social communications through phone calls, messages, emails, social networks and chats that allow them to be in constant contact with friends and family. The data regarding the use of technologies to communicate and get informed, in particular smart phones and mobile phones, testify a capillary diffusion in the world with clear data such as, for example, in Korea where the use rate of smart phones in 2016 was 90%, up to a rate of 99% among

young people between 20 and 30 years of age or in the United States where it was shown that in 2015, two thirds of Americans had a mobile phone with a growing trend in its usage. In 2014, in Spain, 97.1% of young people had a mobile phone and 90.4% of Spanish teenagers used the Internet from their mobile while, in Portugal, it was estimated that 89% of the population had a mobile phone and internet was used by 77% of them. These communicative advantages particularly attract adolescents and young people, who seem to spend a lot of their time using their mobile phones, up to the creation of so-called “cyber spaces”, a sort of virtual space in which to communicate by limiting the social anxieties of appearing with possible negative consequences, in the family and working life of each individual. These devices can therefore produce tolerance that is the growing need to use one’s mobile phone to feel satisfied. Excessive use of smart phones can be considered a form of addiction and can therefore be harmful due to some attitudes and problems that result from their use moreover; disorders such as anxiety and depression have proved to be positive predictors of smart phone addiction. The intrusiveness and persuasiveness of smart phones have developed negative habits among young people that can be assimilated to compulsive behaviours such as: constantly checking the phone for missed messages or calls, checking if there is an available web connection, keeping the phone on 24 hours a day, never going out without the mobile phone, using the phone even during a conversation with another person who is therefore ignored (a condition that characterizes the behaviour defined as “*phubbing*”), believe you have heard the phone ring or “*ringxiety*” a word composed of “*ring*” and “*anxiety*”. All these symptoms culminate in “*Nomophobia*”, which indicates the fear of feeling or remaining disconnected with the possibility of not being able to use the mobile phone and the services it offers, not being able to communicate, losing the connection, information, consequently resulting in feelings of anxiety and anguish due to the loss of the network or if the telephone is discharged. According to Bragazzi and Del Puente nomophobic behaviour is characterized by anxiety of losing coverage or to have low battery; moreover nomophobic persons constantly look at the screen to check the social network updates because they are constantly focused on what is happening among their contacts. The abuse of smart phones can also affect social relationships and ruin their quality, especially in the working environment translating into the neglect of one’s duties and the degradation of relationships between colleagues, also causing unemployment and high staff turnover. In the healthcare setting, where the phenomenon seems to be widespread, these attitudes can have serious repercussions on patients and compromise their health because they can lead to neglecting essential tasks, forgetting important patient data, making careless mistakes and compromising professional patient dialogue, causing a reduction in the quality of the treatments provided. As for nurses, for example, in a study by Gutierrez-Puertas et al., 75% of them admitted to having used their telephone at work for personal problems; other evidence in the literature demonstrates that the problem also seems to affect the nursing training field, specifically nursing students. Although numerous investigations have been carried out on the phenomenon of nomophobia both on nurses and nursing students, the literature does not

seem to report any evidence from the Italian context. Furthermore, there seems to be a lack of information on the comparison between the two populations in question, since the research has focused on the populations studied individually.

But no detailed literature is available regarding an assessment of relationship between smart phone addiction and nomophobia, and whether there has been an effect of smart phone addiction and severity of nomophobia among undergraduate and postgraduate students.

The research gap exists between the previous studies and present study, as in the previous studies, the relationship between smart phone addiction and nomophobia was not assessed. The present study had focused on bridging that gap of assessing the relationship between smart phone addiction and nomophobia. *“Whether there exists an association between smart phone addiction and nomophobia as well as whether there exists an impact during the study period on smart phone addiction and Nomophobia?”* reflected the research question of this study.

3. Objective of the Study

Therefore, here conducted this study with the primary objective of assessment of an impact of Puducherry on smart phone addiction and Nomophobia among Arts and Science college students of Puducherry territorial state of India.

4. Literature Review

King et al. (2014) on 11 individuals with social phobia and showing nomophobic symptoms concluded that the patient diagnosed with social phobia disorder was dependent on the virtual environment to communicate with people whom they were in touch with, and the case was interpreted as avoiding direct social relations with others.

Uysal, Özen, and Madenoğlu (2016) found a low but significant relationship between Nomophobia and social phobia; it was reported that the increased level of Nomophobia caused a predictable increase in social phobia. In another study carried out on individuals with extreme social phobia, smart phones and personal computers were used as an instrument to ease symptoms of social phobia. The findings showed that social phobia behaviors were observed among individuals suffering from non-availability of a smart phone or personal computer, and individuals with disorders accompanying social phobia and obsessive-compulsive disorders were those who were affected by Nomophobia.

Lapointe et al. (2013) investigated addictive smart phone usage via 11 in-depth interviews with participants aged 17–29 years. The data were analyzed using grounded theory and findings suggested that adopting traditional conceptualizations of addiction were not sufficient to define, understand, and manage smart phone addictive behaviors.

Ko (2015) attempted to identify the problems of Christian students' excessive smart phone use in precipitating a psychological and spiritual conflict. Eleven in-depth interviews were conducted among individuals aged 19–26 years and data were analyzed using combination of the phenomenological and qualitative case-study methods. Five categories were derived via phenomenological qualitative analysis that included (a) addiction to smart phones, (b) isolation and alienation, (c) idolization of smart phone, (d) change and spiritual conflicts, and (e) keeping faith in digital world. Overall, the findings reflected that participants experienced both spiritual and psychological conflicts due to high volume of smart phone use.

Tossell et al. (2015) explored smart phone addiction focusing on how self-reported smart phone addiction related to monthly smart phone use. They employed a naturalistic and longitudinal telemetric approach. A total of 34 participants who did not own smart phone were given iPhones installed with program, which operated as a background process and monitored all usage over the course of a yearlong study. At the end of 1 year, users were asked to rate their level of addiction to the smart phone using the Smart phone Addiction Measurement Instrument and the Internet Addiction Test. Two thirds (62%) claimed that they were addicted to their iPhones. The self-defined addicted users and non-addicted users' data were compared on the basis of recorded usage and it was found that self-defined addicted users spent twice as much time on their smart phone and launched applications much more frequently as compared to non-addicted users.

Fix et al. Smartphone addicts with dysphoric moods may find relief online from their symptoms of loneliness, boredom, anxiety, depression, stress, or lack of life satisfaction. Online relationships may substitute for social relationships in person. Addicts with low self-esteem may find that face-to-face inhibitions do not occur online, and they may want to interact with individuals without getting physically or emotionally hurt. Those individuals are trying to escape from the sometimes harsh realities of life.

5. Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted by the Arts and Science colleges of Puducherry territorial state of India over a period of 10 days from July 2022 to August 2022 through a predesigned questionnaire. Inclusion/eligibility criteria adopted for the present study were participants in an age group of 17-25 years, those who were well versed in English language and those who belonged to UG student's category. Under UG category, here it is included students of Arts and Science colleges. Exclusion criteria adopted for the present study were those who did not wish to participate in the study and those who did not belong to above-mentioned UG category. Identity of every participant was strictly kept anonymous. Before starting the survey, all study participants were provided with details of time taken to complete the survey, nature of the survey and information that filling in survey implies provision of informed consent by the participants. Survey questionnaire was circulated by the researcher. Data were collected from study by using the purposive sampling method.

6. Experimental Results

6.1 Distribution of participants with related to their Age

The data presented in below table shows that, majority 81(99%) of the respondents belong to the age group of 17-22 years and 1 (1%) belong to the age group of 23-25 years.

Table1: Distribution of the subject in relation to their age.

S.No	Demographic Variable (Age)	Frequency(F)	Percentage (%)
1.	17-22Years	81	99%
2.	23-25Years	1	1%
3.	Above25 Years	0	0
	Total	82	100%

Fig.1Distribution of the subject in relation to their age

Interpretation: Majority of respondents that is 99% belong to age group of 17 to 22 years as this is the age where the professional course is per sued.

6.2 Distribution of Respondents According to Gender

The data presented in above table shows that, majority 54(65.85%) of the respondents belong to female group of and 28(34.15 %) belong to the male group.

Table2: Distribution of respondents according to gender

S. No	Demographic variables	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Male	28	34.15%
2.	Female	54	65.85%
	Total	82	100.00%

Fig.2 Distribution of respondents according to gender

Interpretation: the research scholar had observed that the majority of samples were female, as nursing is one of the female dominating profession, while other engineering more male could be seen.

6.3 Distribution of Respondents According to Religion

The data presented in above table shows that, majority 34(41.46%) of the respondents belong to Christian group and 28(34.15%) belong to the Hindu religion, while 12(14.63%) belong to Muslim category and remaining are 8(9.76%).

Table3: Distribution of Respondents According to Religion

S. No	Demographic variables - Religion	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Hindu	28	34.15%
2.	Christian	34	41.46%
3.	Muslim	12	14.63%
4.	Others	8	9.76%
	Total	82	100.00%

Fig3.Distribution of Respondents According to Religion

Interpretation: the research scholar found that majority of samples were Christian is 34(41.46%), as being Puducherry, and also the college where research was conducted belong to the Hindu management the remaining 12(15%) were Muslim and rest 10% belong to other religion.

6.4 Distribution of Respondents According to Type of Family

The data presented in above table shows that, majority 52 (63.41%) of the respondents were from nuclear family, 19 (23%) respondents were from joint family and remaining 11 (13.42%) of respondents were from extended family.

Table4: Distribution of respondents according to type of family

S.No	Type of Family	Frequency(F)	Percentage
1.	Nuclear	52	63.41%
2.	Joint	19	23.17%
3.	Extended	11	13.42%
	Total	82	100.00%

Fig4.Distribution of respondents according to type of family

Interpretation: In the present study the research scholar interpreted that majority that is 52(63.41%) sample belong to nuclear family, as in today’s era, many of them stay in nuclear houses as they have travelled along for job or business, remaining 19 (23%) were staying with their grandparents, and only 11(13%) belong to extended family, the extended family still are present at rural.

6.5 Distribution of Scores While Identifying Risk of Nomophobia

Above table reveals the frequency and percentage of respondents having risk of developing nomophobia. The data presented in above table shows that, majority 18(60%) of the respondents were have moderate risk of developing nomophobia, 8 (27%) of respondents were at verge of having severe risk of nomophobia, remaining 4(13 %) of respondents are at mild risk of nomophobia.

Table5: Distribution of scores, identifying risk of nomophobia

S. No	Risk of developing Nomophobia	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Mild	4	13
2.	Moderate	18	60
3.	Severe	8	27

Fig5.Distributionofscores, identifying risk of nomophobia

Above table reveals the frequency and percentage of respondents having risk of developing nomophobia. The data presented in above table shows that, majority 18(60%) of the respondents were have moderate risk of developing nomophobia, 8 (27%) of respondents were at verge of having severe risk of nomophobia, remaining 4(13 %) of respondents are at mild risk of nomophobia.

6.6 Distribution of Respondents According to Utilization of Mobile Phone in Night

Time The data presented in above table shows that, majority 33(40%) of the respondents were using mobile for more than 2 hours in the night time, 12(15%) of respondents were using mobile for1 hours in the night time, 14(17%) respondents were using mobile for 3hours in the night time, 12 (15%) and remaining 11 (13.42%) were using more than 4 hours.

Table6: Distribution of respondents according to utilization of mobile phone in night time

S.No	Demographic Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	1 Hour	12	15.00%
2.	2 Hours	33	40.24%
3.	3 Hours	14	17.07%
4.	4 Hours	11	13.42%
5.	Morethan4 Hours	12	14.63%
	Total	82	100.00%

Fig6.Distribution of respondents according to utilization of mobile phone in night time

Interpretation: the above data shows that majority of sample use their mobile phone for minimum 2 hours in night, as they get that time only to chat, or know, going on. 15% reported that they use it for 1 hour, as many have no work on it, but simply like to visit all sites.

6.7 Distribution of Respondents According to Purpose of Mobile Phone Usage

The data presented in above table shows that, majority 33(40.24%) of the respondents use their mobile for all purpose, 11 (13.42 %) of respondents were using mobile for their personal usage, 14 (17.07%) respondents were using mobile for social purpose while only, 12 (15%) are using mobile phone for academic purpose.

Table7: Distribution of respondents according to purpose of usage

S.No	Demographic Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Academic	12	15.00%
2.	Personnal Use	11	13.42%
3.	Social Websites and Apps	14	17.07%
4.	All the Above	33	40.24%
	Total	82	100.00%

Fig7.Distribution of respondents according to purpose of usage

Interpretation: Majority 40% respondents use mobile for all purpose that is academic, personal, majority of them have the habit of just visiting the sites. While others that are 13% use mobile only for personal use, and are more prone to get addicted.

7. Research Implications

This study is one of the most detailed investigations of Smartphone use in Puducherry, and one of the first to examine Smartphone addiction in academic communities. It is a vital research project, because it providing a comprehensive understanding of the context for Smartphone use among undergraduates (Arts and Science Colleges) in Puducherry. The study can provide guidance for institutions, addiction centers, and families on reasons and solutions of Smartphone addiction among college students. It will, furthermore, assist educators in understanding how students misuse Smart phones to gratify their psychological needs and in suggesting appropriate solutions and alternatives in order to reduce the addiction. The most important task, however, is to make students aware of their Smartphone usage behavior.

8. Limitations: Nomophobia was identified using screening instrument which would not be a proper tool to estimate exact prevalence. This being a cross-sectional study, cause effect relation cannot be ascertained. Finally, as study was done in a closed sample of medical postgraduate students it cannot be generalized to general population.

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